

A NONISOTHERMAL FLOW MODEL FOR RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of heating the fibers in a unidirectional fiber preform during infiltration in resin transfer molding (RTM). The model assumes steady, incompressible flow in the direction of the fibers for nonisothermal conditions with viscosity described by the Arrhenius equation. Temperatures are determined using finite differencing with an iterative scheme to update the viscosity, velocity and temperature down the mold. The results indicate that when compared to isothermal flow with the same initial inlet conditions, the nonisothermal flow profile is "plug-like." A significant reduction in viscosity near the fibers increases the average velocity and decreases the total resin flow time.

Keywords: resin transfer molding, nonisothermal fluid flow, unidirectional fibers, heated fibers

1. INTRODUCTION

This work illustrates the results from a nonisothermal infiltration model of resin transfer molding (RTM) when the fibers of a unidirectional fiber mat preform are heated. The work was initiated because of the desire to reduce the manufacturing time associated with thick parts, parts with complicated geometries, or parts with long gel-time resins. Since thermoset resins initially experience a decrease in viscosity as temperature increases, an obvious method of decreasing processing time is to increase the mold fill rate by raising the resin temperature. While direct heating of the mold, the input resin or the fibers would accomplish the desired result, this model focuses on heating the fibers as it has the added benefit of temperature control through the mold thickness. It is well known that beyond a certain temperature, an exothermic reaction begins, heat is generated, and the viscosity increases rapidly. This study assumes that the temperatures are low enough so as not to initiate the curing process during infiltration.

The majority of fiber infiltration modeling has been performed by considering the resin flow through the preform to be the same process as a fluid flowing through a porous medium. Darcy's Law, which relates the pressure gradient to the velocity, through the fiber permeability and the resin viscosity, has been the basis of these macro-models and the associated numerical simulations and experimental studies. For example, isothermal resin impregnation with a prescribed injection rate

has been modeled by Coulter and Güçeri [1] using a two-dimensional stream function formulation. Martin and Son [2] also considered two-dimensional flow, but used finite element analysis to predict the flow front position. Davé [3] showed that a generalized theory exists which includes fiber consolidation to model a variety of processing methods including RTM [4,5]. Li and Gauvin [6], Bruschke and Advani [7], and Um and Lee [8] have used two-dimensional isothermal Darcy's Law formulations to model the flow front when filling arbitrarily shaped molds. They use finite differencing, finite element, and boundary element methods, respectively. Lin et al. [9] also consider two-dimensional Darcy flow but include the thermal gradients from the exothermic reaction of the resin during cure and heat conduction between the resin and the fiber mat. Their nonisothermal model, permits viscosity variations with temperature only after the onset of resin gelation. A similar approach including viscosity variation was employed by Chan and Hwang [10], but they include the heat transfer from the mold walls and neglect the heat generation from the curing process.

For the nonisothermal macro-models above, the simplification of describing the fiber preform by a permeability constant may limit the understanding of resin flow under fiber heating conditions. For that reason, we developed a simplified micro-model to study the effect of heating fibers during infiltration. The resin flow around fibers is modeled by solving the momentum, energy and mass balance equations for specific fiber array patterns. Existing research pertaining to this area has come from sources which examine flow around cylinders. For example, Sparrow & Loeffler [11] obtained an analytic velocity solution to the longitudinal, fully developed, isothermal flow between cylinders. In a similar study, Sangani and Acrivos [12] examined the contributions of heat transfer to a moving fluid around heated cylinders. They determined the average temperature difference between the bulk fluid and the uniformly heated cylinders. In the latter, no attempt was made to include the variation of viscosity with temperature.

A brief description of the analytical solution and the numerical scheme for determining the velocity profile is provided. Numerical results illustrate the effects of fiber heating on flow response and infiltration times with regard to fiber volume fractions and initial processing temperatures.

2. MODEL DESCRIPTION

2.1. General Description

A micro-model for the nonisothermal flow of a thermoset resin parallel to a unidirectional array of heated fibers is developed from simplified forms of the conservation of momentum and conservation of energy equations. The fibers are held at constant temperature, T_f , which is higher than the inlet temperature, T_o . At the inlet, the resin is injected at a constant pressure, P_o , which is assumed to vary linearly in the z-direction over the solution region (Figure 1). The unidirectional fibers in the mold are arranged in an equilateral triangular array as shown in Figure 2.

2.2. Velocity Solution

To simplify the model, resin velocity, u , and temperature, T , are calculated in an x-y plane perpendicular to the fiber axes assuming steady state conditions at discrete, sequential z-steps. At each z-step, velocity gradients in the flow direction are considered small compared to gradients perpendicular to the flow direction. Density gradients are considered to be negligible. As is common in RTM models, the flow rates are assumed to be small and inertial terms are neglected. With the above assumptions, the momentum equation containing the z-component of velocity is given by a form of Poisson's equation,

$$\nabla^2 u = \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \quad (1)$$

In this equation the viscosity, μ , is allowed to vary with temperature according to the Arrhenius equation,

$$\mu(T) = \mu_0 e^{-\frac{\Delta E}{RT}} \quad (2)$$

where, ΔE is activation energy for the resin and R is the universal gas constant [9].

By the judicious choice of a symmetry bounded region (the shaded areas in Figure 2b) the solution of equation (1) can be formulated in cylindrical coordinates (Figure 2c). A solution for equation (1) with constant pressure gradient in the z -direction and a no-slip boundary condition imposed on

Figure 1. Basic RTM mold model showing solution region.

Figure 2. Solution regions in cross-sectional plane. (a) equilateral triangular array of fibers, the area in dashed lines is that used for the numerical solution. (b) lines of symmetry in triangular array, the hashed area is that used for the analytic velocity solution. (c) details of the analytic velocity solution area in cylindrical coordinates.

the fiber surface was given by Sparrow and Loeffler [11]. Their solution, using eigenfunction expansion, is

$$u(r, \theta) = \left[\frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \right] \left(\frac{r^2 - r_o^2}{4} - \frac{3s^2}{\pi} \ln \left(\frac{r}{r_o} \right) - \frac{s^2}{6} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Delta_n}{nS^{6n}} \left(r^{6n} - \frac{r_o^{12n}}{r^{6n}} \right) \cos(6n\theta) \right) \quad (3)$$

where s is the half-distance between fiber centers, r is the radial distance from the fiber center and r_o is the fiber radius.

2.3. Temperature Solution

The resin is injected at an initial temperature, T_o , and the fibers are held at a constant, elevated temperature of T_f . The steady state energy equation is used to solve for the temperature profile in the resin and then, through equation (2), the resin viscosity profile is calculated. With the low flow rates of RTM, Wymer [13] found that the effects of viscous heating were negligible in the energy formulation. The thermal diffusivity, α , of the resin is assumed constant in the temperature range associated with infiltration. With these considerations the steady state energy equation to be solved is,

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \alpha \nabla^2 T. \quad (4)$$

This convective energy equation is solved numerically for temperature, then equation (2) is used to update the viscosity and this viscosity is used in (3) to produce the velocity profiles at the current z -step [13].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. System Parameters

The parameters for the thermoset resin used in this model are those reported by Lin et al. [9]. All of the resin's thermal parameters are considered constant over the temperature ranges modeled. The resin input pressure was held constant at a value of 0.1 MPa for all of the data shown.

The flow region modeled is 0.25m long in the z -direction. The dimensions in the cross-sectional, X-Y, plane are modeled using a nondimensional ratio $SOR = s/r_o$. This SOR (s over r) ratio is a measure of the free volume available for resin flow and is related to the fiber volume fraction, V_f ; for this work

$$V_f = \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{1}{SOR^2}. \quad (5)$$

3.2. Characteristics of Velocity Profile

The two-dimensional velocity profiles shown in Figure 3 contrast the flow solution for the nonisothermal model, Figure 3b, with a representative isothermal solution, Figure 3a. The two areas of zero velocity in each figure represent one-quarter of a fiber. These velocity profiles show clearly the square, blockish shape which develops in the nonisothermal model. This distinctive shape is most noticeable in the center of the profiles; in this region the isothermal profile rises quadratically and peaks while the nonisothermal velocities rise much more rapidly and plateau in

Figure 3. Comparison of velocity distributions of, (a), the isothermal model with $T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, and (b) the heated fiber model at the $z=0.25$ step with $T_f=100^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_o=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $s=3\text{mm}$, and $V_f=22.67\%$. The characteristic velocity, u_o , is defined as $u_o=\mu_T/\rho l_z$.

the center. This flattened profile results from the competing effects of thermal conduction, from the heated fibers, and forced convective cooling, generated by the increased flow rates away from the zero-velocity fiber surfaces.

The velocity profiles shown in Figure 4 represent velocity values along a line between the fiber centers for successive z -steps down the mold. Figure 4a is the same data as that shown in the two-dimensional profiles of Figure 3. In this figure, the rapid rise in velocity which results from the heated fibers is obvious from a comparison of the initial ($z=0.0$), isothermal step with the profiles shown for the later, nonisothermal steps. The development of the velocity profile from the quadratic-shaped, isothermal profile at the initial z -step to the plug-like, blockish profile for later nonisothermal z -steps is illustrated.

A comparison of the velocity profiles of figures 4a and 4b illustrates the result of the competing thermal effects of conductive heating and convective cooling. Figure 4b shows the profiles for the same SOR ratio as 4a but s , the half-distance between fibers, is smaller (2.0 mm for 4b and 3.0 mm for 4a) and therefore the overall velocities are lower (the velocity for the isothermal 25°C profile for $s=2\text{mm}$ is less than half that for $s=3\text{mm}$). These lower velocities and the smaller fiber separation both allow the conductive heating to dominate at the later steps of the mold in figure 4b. This conductive heating reduces the resin viscosities and allows the continued rise in velocities in the higher flow, center region; this destroys the plug-like shape of the profile.

Figure 4. Comparison of velocity profiles on a line between fiber centers with $T_f=100^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_o=25^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $V_f=22.67\%$; for (a) $s=3\text{mm}$, and for (b) $s=2\text{mm}$.

3.3. Comparison of Flow Times

The measure of average total flow time shown figures 5 and 6 is a relative measure of the time taken for the resin to flow through the 0.25m length of the solution area. This time is calculated by averaging the total times which the resin takes to flow through the solution area for all the finite differencing nodes in the x-y plane. The time taken for the resin flow at each node was determined by dividing the distance between each z-step by the velocity at the previous z-step.

When the fibers are heated the average total flow time drops significantly for all of the fiber volume fraction cases ($V_f=20\%$ to $V_f=50\%$) modeled. From the data of Figure 5 the time savings for the heated fiber flow is 62% over that for isothermal flow at the lowest volume fraction, $V_f=20\%$, and increases to a savings of 78% at the highest volume fraction modeled, $V_f=50\%$. This larger decrease in flow times occurs because of the smaller fiber spacing associated with higher volume fractions. This smaller fiber spacing allows for more efficient conductive heating of the bulk resin by the fibers.

In Figure 6 the dashed curve, showing the variation in flow times as T_f is raised from 25°C to 100°C , represents a much more dramatic reduction in flow times than does the solid curve, showing the change in T_o for the same temperature range. Increasing the fiber temperature 35°C over that of the constant inlet temperature drops the average total flow time from 22.8 sec to 12.2 sec, a reduction of 46.5%; while a similar temperature rise in the inlet temperature drops the flow time only by 3.44%. This shows that increasing fiber heating produces a relative drop in flow times much greater than that of simply raising the inlet temperature, even in the presence of heated fibers.

Figure 5. Comparison of Average total flow time for different fiber volume fractions, $T_f=100^\circ\text{C}$, $T_o=25^\circ\text{C}$, $s=2\text{mm}$.

Figure 6. Comparison of Average total flow time for varying initial temperature conditions, $s=2\text{mm}$, $V_f=22.67\%$.

4. Conclusions

Heating of the fibers produces significantly higher velocities near the fiber surface. If the competing thermal effects of forced convective cooling and heat conduction from heated fibers are balanced properly a blockish, or plug-like velocity profile can be produced. The blockish velocity profile implies an even distribution of flow rates between the fibers.

The heating of the fiber array in this simple RTM produced significant savings in flow time across the solution region. In general any heating of the resin, prior to the onset of cure, will reduce viscosity and therefore increase flow times. However raising of the resin's bulk inlet temperature prior to infiltration and maintaining these elevated temperatures for an extended period of time can increase the risk of premature cure. Controlled heating of fibers, though, yields reductions in flow times comparable to or better than those produced from directly preheating the resin but without the risk of premature gelation.

5. Bibliography

1. Coulter, J.P., Güçeri, S.I., *Resin impregnation during composites manufacturing: Theory and experimentation*, Composite Science and Technology, Vol. 35, pp. 317-330, 1989.
2. Martin, C.Q., Son, J.S., *Fluid mechanics of mold filling for fiber reinforced plastics*, Advanced Composites: The Latest Developments, Proceedings of the ASM/ESD 2nd Conference on Advanced Composites, ed. Beardmore, P., ASM International, 1986, pp. 149-157.
3. Davé, R., *A unified approach to modeling resin flow during composite processing*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 24, pp. 22-41, 1990.

4. Davé, R., Kardos, J.L., Dudukovic, M.P., *A model for resin flow during composite processing: Part I-General Mathematical Development*, Polymer Composites, Vol. 8, pp. 29-38, 1987.
5. Davé, R., Kardos, J.L., Duduković, M.P., *A model for resin flow during composite processing: Part 2-numerical analysis for unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminates*, Polymer Composites, Vol. 8, pp. 123-132, 1987.
6. Li, S., Gauvin, R., *Numerical analysis of the resin flow in resin transfer molding*, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, Vol. 10, pp. 314-327, 1991.
7. Brusckke, M.V., Advani, S.G., Proceedings of SPE., 47th annual technical conference, ANTEC, 1989, p. 1796.
8. Um, M.-K., Lee W.I., *A study of the mold filling process in resin transfer molding*, Polymer Engineering and Science, Vol. 31, pp. 765-771, 1991.
9. Lin, R., Lee, L.J., Liou, M.J., *Nonisothermal mold filling in resin transfer molding and structural reaction injection molding*, Proceedings of 49th Annual Technical Conference - ANTEC '91, Society of Plastics Engineers, 1991.
10. Chan, A.W., Hwang S.-T., *Model of the impregnation process during resin transfer molding*, Polymer Engineering and Science, Vol. 31, pp. 1149-1156, 1991.
11. Sparrow, E.M., Loeffler, A.L., Jr., *Longitudinal laminar flow between cylinders arranged in regular array*, American Institute of Chemical Engineers Journal, Vol. 5, pp. 325-330, 1959.
12. Sangani, A.S., Acrivos, A., International Journal of Multiphase Flow, Vol. 8, pp. 193-206, 1982.
13. Wymer, S.A., *Analysis of resin flow parallel to an array of heated fibers in resin transfer molding*, Masters of Science Thesis, Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA., 1992.